

FOCCUS

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D8.1 Inventory of Applications

WP8: Applications to support MS requirements

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About this document

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Glossary and Abbreviations

ADRIFS	Adriatic Forecasting System
BGC	Biogeochemical
BIAS	Arithmetic Bias
CF	Climate Forecast (Convention for NetCDF)
CFL	Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy condition
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center of Climate Change
CNR	National Research Council (Italy)
DELTARES	Stichting Deltares
DPV	Data Product Validation
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DCSM	Delft3D Coastal Systems Model
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EDITO-ML	EDITO Model Lab
EO	Earth Observation
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ESC	Environmental and Societal Challenges
EU	European Union
FABM	Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Model
FOCCUS	Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users
GCOAST-GB	German Bright
HABs	Harmful Algal Blooms
HBM	HIROMB-BOOS Model
HEREON	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon
HR	High-Resolution
HFR	High-Frequency Radar
HS	Significant Wave Height
ICG-EMO	OSPAR Intersessional Correspondence Group on Ecological Modelling
ILVO	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
ISAR	Infrared Sea Surface temperature Autonomous Radiometer
LoC	Land Ocean Continuum
LCFS	Lazio Coast Forecasting System
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MHWs	Marine Heatwaves
MHD	Marine Hydrographic Directorate (Romania)
MED-MFC	Mediterranean Monitoring Forecasting System
MERIS	Envisat Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer
MET.NO	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
MOI	Mercator Ocean International
MSCS	Member States Coastal System
MFSD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSI	MultiSpectral Instrument
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NRT	Near Real Time
NWS	North-West Shelf
ODP	Operational Data Product
OGCM	Ocean Global Circulation Model
OSPAR	The Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
OSERIT	Oil Spill Evaluation and Response Integrated Tool
PU	Public
RBINS	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
ROFI	Region Of Freshwater Influence

S2	Sentinel-2
S3	Sentinel-3
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SDB	Satellite-Derived Bathymetry
SAV	Submerged Aquatic Vegetation
SCHISM	Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydroscience Integrated System Model
SHOM	Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine
SOCIB	Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
SSH	Sea Surface Height
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
STD	Standard Deviation
TWL	Total Water level
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WiS	What-If-Scenarios
WMOP	Western Mediterranean Operational Model
WP	Work Package
WW3	WaveWatch III®
XBEACH	Cross-shore Beach Dynamics Model

1. Executive Summary

The **FOCCUS project** (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) aims to improve and advance the coastal dimension of CMEMS and **demonstrate** a convincing leverage and coupling of CMEMS and Member State Coastal System (MSCS) for advancing knowledge about the coastal environment and associated applications.

Work Package 8 (WP8) focuses on demonstrating the usefulness of the advancements in the observing and modelling systems through the co-design of applications, which aid three Environmental and Societal Challenges (ESCs).

This report provides an overview of the various applications designed as part of each ESC, thereby reporting on:

- **Task 8.1** Design of applications to better manage and protect the coastal area (ESC 1).
- **Task 8.2** Design of applications to enhance the blue economy (ESC 2).
- **Task 8.3** Design of application related to natural and anthropogenic hazards and resilience to climate change (ESC 3).

The report is divided into two sections, where each subsection in **Section 2** maps the individual applications dedicated to a specific ESC. Each application description outlines the application objective, the usage and value of observations (WP2), land-ocean models (WP4) and Member State Coastal System improvements (WP6), the expected outputs, fit for purpose validation and end users. **Section 3** describes the next steps (WP9) and common challenges which will be given attention.

Overall, the co-design of the coastal applications has been successfully completed, beginning with the milestone MS10.4: Co-Design Workshop with stakeholders in M6 (see [Annex](#)) and culminating in the milestone MS8.1: Applications Definition Workshop during M14 of the project, in which the applications were discussed by the entire Consortium (see [Annex](#)). Technical design choices and links with the three pillars of FOCCUS (coastal observations, hydrology, coastal modelling improvements) have been clarified in sufficient detail. Local stakeholders have been involved in this co-design process.

While expected improvements and validation strategies have been outlined, the ultimate success of the coastal applications depend on the demonstrated improvements compared to the current state-of-the-art systems.

2. Inventory of Coastal Applications

The design of FOCCUS coastal applications aims at demonstrating how to better address selected environmental and societal challenges, compared to state-of-the-art. Within Member State Coastal Systems, the selected environmental and societal challenges (ESCs) to manage and protect the coastal zone, support sustainable blue economy, and build resilience of the coastal zone, will be targeted.

Each application outlines the usage and shows the value of observations (WP2) and models (WP4 & WP6) improvements, which form the backbone of coastal applications demonstrations. Additionally, the application objective, the expected outputs, fit for purpose validation and targeted stakeholders and end users (intermediate users) are described.

The selected ESCs reflect general targets of the applications, with specificities of challenges to be addressed in different regions and basins (see Figure 1). The FOCCUS applications aim to provide benchmarks to be used in other contexts and be scalable with a pan-European focus.

Figure 2: Visual depiction of all coastal applications, their location and main topic. Yellow applications refer to ESC 1 (section 2.1 of the deliverable), blue applications refer to ESC 2 (section 2.2 in the deliverable) and green applications refer to ESC 3 (section 2.3 in the deliverable).

2.1 Applications to better manage and protect the coastal area (ESC 1)

In this section, the described coastal applications will address pollution and coastal erosion focusing on the role of Land Ocean Continuum (LoC), coastal dynamics and connectivity across nations and regions.

2.1.1 Pollution hazard/risk mapping

2.1.1.1 Land-based pollution and eutrophication in the North Sea

Application Objective:

Assess the impact of land-based (nutrient) pollution on eutrophication in the North Sea within the OSPAR Assessment Areas.

Within this application, the impact of land-based (nutrient) pollution on various eutrophication variables will be assessed per OSPAR assessment areas. This application intends to serve efforts of the OSPAR Intersessional Correspondence Group on Ecological Modelling (ICG-EMO).

This work addresses two policy indicators:

- MSFD descriptor D5, Eutrophication: “Human-induced eutrophication is minimised, especially adverse effects thereof, such as losses in biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, harmful algae blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters”.
- OSPAR’s Operational Objective S1.O3: By 2024 identify and quantify relevant sources, including transboundary transport, and agree nutrient reduction needs for each Contracting Party to [not exceed/stay below] the maximum input levels, reporting on progress in 2025 and regularly thereafter.

Application definition:

The application focuses on the OSPAR Assessment Areas in the NWS, for a 2-year study set from 2015 to 2017. While the underlying model is the Dutch Continental Shelf Model, a MSCS, the application serves not a single Member State but a transboundary assessment, since the far-field impacts of pollution are considered. The inflow, spread and interaction of nutrients (NH₄, NO₃, PO₄) from rivers and open boundaries (North Atlantic and Baltic) will be modelled, and the effect of these nutrients on predicted Chlorophyll-a, and other eutrophication indicators will be assessed (Figure 2.1.1.1, left).

By conducting a study with total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) as conservative tracers, the reach of total nutrient concentrations from river discharges and their relative contribution per OSPAR assessment area could be evaluated (Figure 2.1.1.1, right).

Fig 2.1.1.1.1: Left: Chlorophyll-a (90-percentile) annual mean per assessment area. Right: Relative contribution of river sources to annual mean total-P concentration per assessment area.

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>The existing technology is an adapted 3D Dutch Continental Shelf Model (DCSM) with hydrodynamics and water quality modelling, previously used for OSPAR Eutrophication Assessment (Lenhart et al., 2022; van Leeuwen et al., 2023, Prins et al., 2023). This model uses the Delft3D FM (flexible mesh) modelling suite, where D-Flow FM (hydrodynamics module) and D-Water Quality (water quality module) are coupled online. Instead of modelling sediment transport, a forcing field of Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) is used. The old forcing is a yearly averaged MERIS satellite data of SPM with a cosine function imposed on it to get seasonal variations (Nechad et al., 2010) with improvement in the Wadden Sea by using 100 x 100 m Sentinel-2 satellite data instead of MERIS for that area.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More stable temperature and salinity vertical profiles in deeper oceanic areas, resulting in higher accuracy compared to previous model versions. - Improved chlorophyll-a concentrations compared to previous model versions due to improved primary production calculations from enhanced SPM forcing fields.
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model validation with Coastal data, when applicable (D2.1 Data Product 3.14).

Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Update river inputs with the improved E-HYPE4 product (D4.2 Chapter 3) for the entire model domain.
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving consistency in physics between CMEMS NEMO and 3D DCSM-FM on thermobaricity: taking pressure into account in the Equation of State. (D6.1 4.1.1) - Replace old Suspended Particulate Matter forcing with weekly CMEMS satellite data, gap-filled with the 4DVarNet deep learning algorithm. (D6.1 4.1.2)
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eutrophication OSPAR indicators (e.g. chlorophyll-a growing season mean, nutrient winter mean) maps, following the OSPAR Common Procedure - Maps showing relative nutrient contribution of rivers in OSPAR assessment areas
Fit for purpose validation:	<p>Validation of BGC variables based on monthly means or seasonal means that better support the analysis of BGC cycles in the NWS. OceanPredict “Class 1” metrics and OceanPredict “Class 4” metrics: spatial maps, time series, Taylor diagrams, and tables of estimated accuracy metrics for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature (sea surface and bottom) - Chlorophyll-a (sea surface) - Dissolved Oxygen (bottom) - Nutrients (sea surface)
End Users/Stakeholders:	<p>Operators of the MSCS (Deltares), Dutch Ministry for Infrastructure and Water management, Directorate-General for Public Works and Water Management (Rijkswaterstaat, RWS), OSPAR Intersessional Correspondence Group on Ecological Modelling</p>
Provider:	<p>Deltares</p>
Further information	<p>None</p>

2.1.1.2 Mapping coastal benthic habitats impacted by sediment plumes

Application Objective:

Dredging, dredge disposal, and sand extraction on the Belgian Continental Shelf disturb the seabed and resuspend large volumes of sediment. These licensed activities are monitored through:

1. Activity Monitoring: Each dredging vessel carries a “black box” that records data (e.g., location, sediment volume), allowing estimation of sediment resuspension.
2. Environmental Impact Monitoring: Conducted by FPS Economy, RBINS, and ILVO, this assesses effects on the seabed, habitats, and ecosystem components. Results support Belgium's EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) obligations, particularly descriptor D6C2 (physical disturbance).

Although near-field impacts are well-studied, far-field effects from sediment plume dispersion remain unclear. A new modeling system is being developed to simulate and quantify plume spread, assess cumulative impact, and support indicators of pressure on sensitive habitats. Once validated, it will help link local disturbances (D6C2) to broader ecosystem effects (D6C4/D6C5) via MSFD descriptors D7C1 and D7C2, promoting more sustainable practices.

Application definition:

Area of Interest : The Belgian territorial waters and the Belgian EEZ.

Variables considered :

- as input : resuspended sediment volume, current, waves, turbulence diffusivity
- as output : sediment dispersion footprint and pressure on benthic habitat concentration.

Spatial and temporal extent : sediment dispersion footprint and pressure on benthic habitat can be computed for a single event (duration a few days), or by integrating all the dredging and dumping events occurring on a daily basis, weekly basis, monthly basis or even yearly basis.

Expected outputs :

Figure 2.1.1.2.1. Left: Preliminary map displaying the far-field pressure on the benthic habitats due to all sand extraction activities occurred on the Belgian continental shelf in 2019. The pressure units are ‘kg of sediment per seconds’. This map has been produced using the OSERIT-SEDIM system and presented at the Belgian Stakeholder in October 2024 (Van Lancker et al., 2024). Right: Broadscale benthic habitat map. Combining the two maps shall give information on the pressure exerted on sensitive gravel beds (aka “offshore circalittoral sediment” in brownish).

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>OSERIT is a suite of Lagrangian particle models developed, maintained, and operated by the RBINS Marine Forecasting Centre to originally support the activities of the Belgian Kustwacht partners. Since its inception in 2009, OSERIT has been continuously improved through several projects and applications. In 2024, The ‘OSERIT-drift’ source code was completely refactored and publicly released on a public GitHub repository. This open-source model contains OSERIT’s core functionality, from which different OSERIT applications can be built. According to the application, Lagrangian particles can represent floating objects, sediments, oil spills, chemical spills, fish larvae, etc. For each particle type, specific parameterizations representing specific behaviours can be activated or deactivated. In particular, the OSERIT-SEDIM includes specific parametrization t such as settling velocity or deposition and resuspension processes.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<p>upgrading the met-ocean forcing used in OSERIT-SEDIM from OPTOS-V1 (horizontal resolution of 750m) to OPTOS-V3 (horizontal resolution of 150m).</p>
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<p>A preliminary discussion with the partner Borckmann-Consult has been initiated in order to get satellite observation of the near-surface overflow sediment plume in the Belgian EEZ, including L3 for irradiance, turbidity and SPM concentration for the year 2019. Unfortunately if these data exists in CMEMS products catalog for a stripe of 20km from the shoreline (e.g. OCEANCOLOUR_NWS_BGC_HR_L3_NRT_009_203), such data does</p>

	not cover the full EEZ. Unfortunately, these data sets have not been envisaged in D2.1 and D2.2.
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	N/A
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	The application will use the high-resolution simulations produced by the Belgian Coastal System OPTOSv3 (FOCCUS D6.1).
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An on-demand modelling system based on OSERIT-SEDIM that simulates the drift and fate of sediment plumes resuspended by human activities. This system shall be accurate enough to represent the large-scale far-field impacts of human activities occurring at a dredging vessel scale (a few hundreds of meters). - A clear definition of the pressure indicator - A showcase data set for 2019 (product)
Fit for purpose validation/calibration:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The black boxes data of all dredging and sand extractions vessels have been collated for year 2019. - Observations data set collated in the framework of the national project TURBEAMS (https://www.belspo.be/belspo/NewRV/projects/TURBEAMS_en.pdf), including acoustic datasets and granulometric composition of these sand extraction plumes
End Users/Stakeholders:	<p>All actors and stakeholders involved in the value chain of the sand extraction activities, dredging activities and disposal of dredged material.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The dredging companies such as Jan De Nul and DEME operate the dredging vessels - The Belgian Federal Public Service “Economy” manages the sand extraction activities. - The Flemish Agency “Maritieme Toegang” manages the dredging operations in maritime Fairways - The Belgian Federal Public Service “Environment” and RBINS are respectively in charge of the reporting and the assessment of the good environmental status of the marine environment in Belgium (MSFD, WFD, etc.) - The research center RBINS, ILVO and VLIZ are involved in monitoring or research activities.
Provider:	RBINS
Further Information:	<p>OSERIT source code (core model) :</p> <p>https://github.com/naturalsciences/OSERIT-drift</p>

2.1.2 Coastal erosion dynamics assessment

2.1.2.1 Coastal erosion dynamics assessment of the Mediterranean Sea

Application Objective:

This application aims to enhance the representation of wave–circulation–sediment interactions by integrating a sediment transport module with circulation and wave models. The goal is to improve the identification and evaluation of coastal erosion processes along the Northern Adriatic Sea, with a particular focus on the Emilia-Romagna region—an area frequently impacted by extreme events that drive erosion and coastal flooding. The coupled modeling framework will enable the analysis of sediment dynamics and the identification of vulnerable coastal zones, contributing to risk assessment and supporting coastal planning and hazard mitigation efforts. What-if scenarios will support the investigation of specific extreme events.

Fig. 2.1.2.1 Left: Preliminary results of simulated Suspended Sediment concentration at the Po river delta; Right: difference with satellite data (right)

Application definition:

The application focuses on the Adriatic–Mediterranean region, specifically in Italy, with reference to the Adriatic Forecasting System (AdriFS) as a Member State Coastal System. Its main objective is to improve the coupling between wave, circulation, and sediment processes to support erosion risk assessment in the Mediterranean Sea. The simulation will be conducted over the course of one year (to be confirmed with Seimur) and will provide key outputs related to erosion processes, including current fields, bottom stress, significant wave height and direction, near-bottom orbital velocity, and suspended sediment concentration. The domain includes the Adriatic Sea and the northern Ionian Sea, spanning from 12° to 21°E and from 39° to 45.8°N, with a horizontal unstructured-grid resolution ranging from 2.5 km in the open sea to 300 m along the coast.

Existing Technology:

AdriFS is a coupled modeling framework that integrates ocean and wave models, based on SHYFEM-MPI and the state-of-the-art third-generation community wave model WAVEWATCH III. The modeling approach is based on the downscaling of CMEMS products

	and currently features a two-way coupled wave–circulation system. However, it does not yet include a sediment module.
Designed Improvements:	This application aims to improve knowledge of sediment dynamics along the Emilia-Romagna coastal area thanks to the use of a sediment module in the coupled system, rather than relying on circulation as a proxy, and by incorporating improved river inputs developed within the project.
Links with observations components (WP2/3)	For validation, data from D2.1 will be used, including sea surface height (SSH) from remote sensing (D2.1, product 2.1.1) Additionally, upcoming coastal data from D2.1 (product 2.3.2) will be used for validation with in situ observations.
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	Land-Ocean Continuum: Improved freshwater inputs for the Po river from D4.2 (product 4.1) and Estuary Box Model MS4.1 (4.1)
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	This application utilizes the MSCS “AdriFS” system and inherits improvements from D6.1 and D6.2. The modelling framework will be enhanced with improved lateral boundary conditions, particularly through the implementation of methods for reconstructing multipartitioned spectra, and coastal data assimilation techniques.
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	Maps for one year (eg 2019) showing averaged fields relevant to sediment dynamics, including currents, and near-bottom orbital velocity. Maps presenting erosion risk indicators, based on mean values and percentiles of suspended sediment concentration and bottom shear stress.
Fit for purpose validation:	The validation of the wave and circulation models itself will be performed using in-situ and remote observations available within the domain for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Sea level · Significant Wave height Validation of Suspended sediment concentration will be qualitatively evaluated using satellite data. Key validation metrics include RMSE, bias, correlation, and scatter index.
End Users/Stakeholders:	Key stakeholders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Institute: Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) Thematic: coastal protection, extreme events ● Institute: Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna, Italy Thematic: coastal protection, extreme events ● Institute: AMA-Coopmare Thematic: Aquaculture/ShellFish farming

Provider:	CMCC, CNR
Further Information:	None

2.1.2.2 Coastal erosion dynamics assessment of the German North Sea with cross-scale models

Application Objective:

This application aims to assess the dynamics and risks associated with coastal erosion along the German North Sea coast, particularly in response to hydrodynamic extreme events.

By integrating both direct (morphodynamic modeling) and indirect (hydrodynamic conditions combined with sedimentological information) modeling approaches, the application will generate spatially explicit risk maps indicating areas susceptible to erosion. Additionally, it will provide regional forecasts of bed level changes following storm events. Furthermore, the application enables the exploration of mitigation strategies for coastal erosion through "what-if" scenario analyses, evaluating the effectiveness of coastal vegetation as a natural buffer against storm-induced erosion.

Application definition:

The application focuses on the German territorial Waters in the North Sea for a 1-year study period set in 2017. Therefore Germany is the primarily addressed Member state, however the System also includes the Danish Wadden Sea enabling transboundary assessments in this area. The simulation activities will provide fields for erosion relevant hydro- (Currents, bed stress), Wave dynamics (Significant Wave Height (HS), wave direction) and Sediment concentrations, as well as regionally nested (Xbeach) simulations of bed level changes in particular in response to storm events.

The application will further explore What-if-Scenarios (WiS) and provide information on how the implementation of coastal vegetation attenuates these variables and thus could reduce coastal erosion risks.

Fig.2.1.2.2 Left: Erosion risk assessment based on relative amount of time succeeding the critical shear stress average of local sediment grain size composition (0% < No < 25% < low < 50% < increased < 75% < high). Right: Reduction in risk level bins in presence of extended coastal vegetation.

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>The existing technology encompasses the GCOAST-GB configuration, which integrates hydrodynamic modeling (SCHISM), wave modeling (WWM; Roland et al., 2012), and sediment transport modeling (Pinto et al., 2012). These components are coupled at the source-code level within the SCHISM modeling framework (Zhang et al., 2016). To allow for higher-resolution morphological assessments, the system includes regionally nested XBeach configurations. The unstructured grid modeling system GB configuration scales up in resolution toward coastal areas at risk of erosion, reaching grid resolutions of 200–300 meters, and incorporates wetting and drying processes. It is nested within the CMEMS NWS product to provide hydrodynamic boundary conditions. Additionally, a Hereon-developed in-house configuration of WaveWatch III, covering the North East Atlantic and North Sea, supplies spectral boundary data for the WWM wave model component. The GCOAST-GB system delivers a wide range of outputs, including hydrodynamic variables (e.g., sea surface elevation, currents, temperature, salinity, and bed stresses), Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) concentrations, and wave characteristics such as significant wave height, direction, and period. A highly resolved (5-meter grid) local XBeach model for the island of Norderney directly simulates morphological changes. Both the SCHISM and XBeach model components incorporate parameterizations for coastal vegetation, enabling the assessment of vegetation-induced wave and current attenuation, and thus providing insight into potential risk reduction measures.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<p>Expected are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved SPM simulation by implementing relaxation (nudging [NUDG]) techniques in the model surface layer to assimilate satellite-observed SPM concentrations [] using nudging [NUDG] analog as for Temperature and Salinity (WP6.1 report, P38). This approach aims to better constrain the model and improve representation of spatiotemporal SPM variability
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The seagrass and macroalgae data (D2.1.3, D2.1 section 3.6.1) will be used to implement seagrass locations for the WiS in the part of the Domain covered by these data - For Validation data data from D2.1 on SSH (Remote Sensed SSH, D21 Section 4.1) and SST (Fiducial reference SST observations, D.21 Section 3.12.2)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From D2.3 upcoming Coastal Data (D.2.1, Chapter 3.14) will be used for Validation with in situ-observations
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Update river inputs with the improved E-HYPE4 product (D4.2 Chapter 3) for the entire model domain.
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This application utilizes the MSCS “GCOAST-GB” (German Bight, 6.1) model System nested within the CMEMS NWS shelf product and the in 6.1 mentioned improvements.
Expected outputs/ target products- indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps of individual hydrodynamic, wave, and SPM variables, showing key statistics (temporal means and 95th percentiles). - Comparative maps illustrating changes in hydrodynamic, wave, and SPM statistics (temporal mean, 95th percentile) in response to coastal vegetation as a mitigation strategy. - Maps showing Erosion risk indicators, based on grain size composition dependent succeeding times of critical shear stress. - Maps of changes in individual hydrodynamic, Wave and SPM variable statistics (temporal mean, 95th percentile) in response to applying coastal vegetation as mitigation strategy. - Maps showing Erosion risk indicator changes, based on grain size composition dependent succeeding times of critical shear stress in response to applying coastal vegetation.
Fit for purpose validation:	<p>Model validation will be performed using in-situ observations, including data from tide gauges and wave buoys. Particular emphasis will be placed on evaluating model performance during storm events to ensure fitness for purpose in high-impact scenarios.</p> <p>In addition, a model-to-model comparison will be carried out against the CMEMS NWS product to assess consistency and reliability.</p> <p>Validation results will be quantified using standard error metrics, including bias, root mean square error (RMSE), and relative standard deviation. These metrics will be visualized through illustrative time series plots and Taylor diagrams to clearly communicate model performance.</p> <p>Satellite imagery will be consulted for qualitative comparisons with erosion risks and morphological simulation in near shore areas.</p>
End Users/ Stakeholders:	<p>Operators of the Member State Coastal System (Hereon)</p> <p>Key Stakeholders:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NLWKN; Lower Saxon State Department for Waterway, Coastal and Nature Conservation, Regional/local authority (data users and producers) - Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung (KDM) / German Marine Research Consortium; Non-profit Association of Research Institutes, Science Policy and Science Strategy (data users) - Gute Küste Niedersachsen (data users) - The Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH) (data users and providers)
Provider:	Hereon
Further Information:	None

2.1.2.3 Coastal erosion dynamics assessment of the North-Western Black Sea with cross-scale models

Application Objective:

Assessment of erosional risk along North-Western Black Sea coast driven by hazardous sea state conditions related to sea-level height and wave climate.

This application relies on a seamless scale hydrodynamic-wave-sediment model (SCHISM) assisted by a morphological model (XBeach). This combined approach allows assessing erosion risk from the open sea to small sandy beaches. The assessment will identify and characterize spatially the main drivers for the erosional risk. Considering climate treats, mitigation plans will be explored through What-If Scenarios by the use of Nature-based solutions. Furthermore, both models will provide operational forecasting and monitoring of extreme conditions.

Application definition:

The applications cover the entire transboundary area of North-Western Black Sea. This area addresses the territory of two Member States, Bulgaria and Romania, including the territory of Ukraine.

The functionalities encompass outputs for the currents, wave fields, shear bottom stress and sediment concentration. Those outputs will be characterized for storm events and their impacts over the coast and interaction with seagrass meadows. To contextualize with climate scenarios prognosed for the area, the What-if experiments will frame future risk scenarios. Regarding the spatial domain, the SCHISM setup will cover the entire continental shelf, while the XBeach model will provide a detailed estimate for the bed level changes in the selected list of sandy beaches. A preliminary study and validation for changes in the shoreline will be conducted for the period 2020-2023.

Fig 2.1.2.3 Snapshots from the GCOAST-BS domain models illustrating the interaction between the SCHISM and XBeach models. The magnitude of frictional stress across the Northwestern Black Sea is shown at the shelf-sea scale, while the high-resolution bathymetry within the XBeach domain captures morphological processes at the nearshore scale.

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>The GCOAST-BS set-up integrates the hydrodynamical model SCHISM, the wave model WWM and the sediment model SED3D in an unstructured mesh with variable size. For small subgrids, GCOAST-BS uses the XBeach model to compute morphodynamics. The current setup for the SCHISM model applies a nudging layer to the salinity and temperature fields. The WWM model is forced by a parametric wave spectra built from CMEMS wave variables.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<p>Expected are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved SPM simulation via relaxation (nudging) towards satellite derived SPM observations - Improved coastal buoyancy representation via river forcing from E-HYPE, which will include new branches from the Danube Delta into the coast.

Links with observations components (WP2/3)	- Satellite derived shorelines, bathymetries, mean sea level and granulometry from the beach monitoring products from D2.1.
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	- River inputs with the improved E-HYPE4 product for the Danube Delta branches and the river data from EFAS/LISFLOOD (D4.2). - Identification of Regions of freshwater Influence (ROFI) as interface areas (D4.2.2).
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	- This application utilizes the MSCS “GCOAST-BS” (Northwestern Black Sea, 6.1) model System and CMEMS products for the Black Sea.
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	- Maps indicating thresholds for hazardous conditions, based on temporal means and 95th percentiles of each variable related to the sea state conditions. - Maps for comparative scenarios to measure the effectiveness of Based-nature solutions. - Maps showing erosion risk indicators, based on grain characteristics and mobility under extreme intense bed level shear stress.
Fit for purpose validation:	The Northwestern Black Sea is monitored along key port regions by in-situ instruments and by operational remote sensing products at Level-3 and Level-4. The validation will be addressed considering the availability of observation during extreme events at different locations. In-situ data will be employed for quantitative validation using hydrographic and wave variables and remote sensing data. The validation will be measured by the bias, root mean square error and relative standard deviation. Long-term shoreline changes and sediment transport estimates will be qualitatively validated against model estimates. The qualitative validation will compare the net tendency for erosion and deposition derived from the observations with the model results.
End Users/Stakeholders:	Operators of the Member State Coastal System (Hereon) Key Stakeholders: Marine Research, MSFD, WFD, MSF, geological and geophysical studies within the Danube – Danube Delta – Black Sea: - National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa" Constanta (NIMRD) - The National Institute for Research and Development on Marine Geology and Geo-ecology – GeoEcoMar Constanța Branch (GeoEcoMar) - Danube Delta National Institute (DDNI)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MSFD implementation: Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests; NIMRD; GeoEcoMar - Water Framework Directive (WFD): NIMRD, National Administration of Romanian Waters etc. - National Regulatory Authority for Mining, Petroleum and Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide; Non-governmental organisations and the dredging / oil and gas companies (OMV-Petrom; Black Sea Oil and Gas). - Marine Cluster Bulgaria
Provider:	Hereon
Further Information:	None

2.2 Applications to enhance the blue economy (ESC 2)

2.2.1 Support to multi-use coastal and off-shore operations

In this section, the described coastal applications will support multi-use coastal and offshore operations, including methodologies to improve early warning systems for risks (e.g. HABs, heatwaves, storms).

2.2.1.1 Support of aquaculture and offshore operations in Norway

Application Objective:

The aquaculture industry is very important to the Norwegian economy and digital solutions for decision support and monitoring is critical for safe operations and efficient management. Examples include handling of salmon lice infestation pressures, or other pathogens, or monitoring risk for harmful algae blooms (HABs). The physical-biological couplings are strong. Especially the transport of pathogens is closely coupled to the transient circulation features inside Norway's long fjords, and the exchange processes with the open ocean. There are also direct links between the physical environment and the pathogens. For instance, salmon lice larvae are sensitive to salinity, and also mature at a temperature dependent rate. Monitoring of pathogens are based on offline drift models using inputs from ocean circulation models. HABs are difficult to predict, and when they appear, fish farm operators are often required to move installations: a challenging operation that benefits from real-time information about currents and hydrography.

The main objective is to improve the coastal ocean circulation model representation of the hydrography, the fjord-open ocean connectivity, and the near-surface circulation.

Application definition:

The area of interest is the Norwegian coast, with a focus on the southwestern parts. The demonstration includes two components: one coastal ocean circulation model, and one drift trajectory model. The main variables we will consider are currents, salinity, and temperature.

Fig. 2.2.1.1: Example of particle drift in a Norwegian fjord, with associated changes in environmental properties (salinity and temperature) along the drift path.

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>The technology is based on the ROMS ocean circulation model, and a Python based offline drift trajectory modeling system OpenDrift.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<p>Improvements are expected from a better representation of the freshwater forcing in the fjords, and also from an improved representation of the shelf dynamics from assimilating coastal observations. Our ability to model the circulation in the fjords is closely linked to our coastal ocean model's ability to capture the conditions on the shelf (Dalsøren <i>et al.</i>, 2020). Usually the fjords are salinity stratified, which means that the river discharge data are crucial in the forcing, and there are also strong physical-biological couplings in downstream services for salmon lice monitoring, since the salmon lice larvae can only survive within certain salinity ranges.</p>
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<p>Surface currents from HF radar, and potentially Doppler SAR (T2.2.2, Sea-level and currents (Version 1) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14825347)</p>
<p>Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)</p>	<p>Improved river runoff data from E-HYPE (D5.2).</p>
<p>Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)</p>	<p>Using MSCS "Norkyst". Related tasks are T6.1.2, improved nesting to CMEMS models, with focus on doing bias correction of the external boundary conditions; T6.3.1, data assimilation, with use of HF radar data and potentially SAR Doppler for data assimilation, evaluating usefulness for upper ocean dynamics through impact assessments; and T6.3.2, diagnostics, with dedicated scripts to analyse hydrography, upper ocean currents, and drift trajectories.</p>

Expected outputs/ target products- indicators:	From a stakeholder perspective, the most important output is an improved description of the coastal ocean dynamics in the circulation model: trajectory models tailored for various uses (oil spills, salmon lice, viral loads, fish larvae, etc.) are already in place in relevant institutions that provide decision support or are involved in management, hence we will use our own trajectory modeling system for diagnostics.
Fit for purpose validation:	<p>Validation efforts will focus on salinity and temperature through water mass distributions, freshwater dynamics, and stability. For the shelf dynamics, HF-radar measurements will be used, too.</p> <p>Relevant variables and derived quantities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Salinity, temperature, surface currents, - T/S-diagrams - Freshwater height - Profile potential energy anomaly - Turner angle <p>More in-depth assessment of water column stability and air-sea fluxes will be done in selected areas for periods of special interest (to be identified in discussions with stakeholders, but typically these will be warm periods in spring/summer).</p>
End Users/ Stakeholders:	Institute of Marine Research, aquaculture industry.
Provider:	MET.NO
Further Information:	None

2.2.1.2 Off-shore windfarm operation & co-use of resources in the German Bight

<p>Application Objective:</p> <p>The Blue Economy Application for the German Bight is a virtual framework that models the operation of energy production facilities, such as offshore wind farms, and food production facilities, such as aquaculture. The virtual framework is centred on the unstructured model SCHISM for the German Bight, incorporating configuration physics and biogeochemistry. The FABM is used as an interface for the coupling of hydrodynamics and biogeochemical turnover. The equations for lower-trophic-level aquaculture are also managed via FABM. The application ensures hind-cast and NRT simulation and is scenario-capable, e.g. to simulate and evaluate utilisation strategies of joint wind energy use and food production. The application is also able to support the maintenance and operation of the blue economy by producing relevant oceanic data.</p>
<p>Application definition:</p> <p>The area of interest is the German Bight of the North Sea. Relevant outputs are significant wave height, mean wave direction, phytoplankton biomass or chlorophyll, oxygen concentration and aquaculture production potential.</p>

Fig 2.2.1.2 Area of interest with average summer chlorophyll concentration as estimated in the numerical model SCHISM-FABM-ECOSMO.

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>The SCHISM-FABM-ECOSMO model is available for coastal areas with complex topography with wetting-and drying (Pein et al., 2021). The model application uses the Copernicus Marine products NWSHELF_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_004_013 and NWSHELF_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_004_002 for lateral forcing.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of Offshore wind energy structures adding ultra-high resolution including representation of the windfarm monopiles, development of physical parameterizations supporting the resulting high gradients of horizontal resolution - Implementation of lower-trophic level aquaculture: integration of additional state variables and kinetic reactions accounting for growth of aquaculture species like blue mussel; diversification of model tracer transport disabling advection and diffusion for aquaculture state variables - Steps towards operational service: automated processing of model forcing and automated job launched to generate daily forecasts of the coupled physical-biological model
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - satellite observations for calibration and validation of the phytoplankton component, e.g. OCEANCOLOUR_NWS_BGC_HR_L4_NRT_009_209 (D2.1): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mass concentration of chlorophyll a in sea water CHL [mg/m³] - Mass concentration of suspended matter in sea water SPM [g/m³]
<p>Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EHype river runoff for improved lateral forcing of nutrient loads as a function of river runoff

Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated with the GCOAST-GB modelling system sharing workflows and routines.
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	Users and stakeholders receive more precise information on ocean dynamics including windwaves and phytoplankton dynamics in a key economic area of the southern North Sea. Outputs such as significant wave height, wave direction, oxygen concentration and total chlorophyll can support the planning of blue economy activities such as offshore wind energy and aquaculture production.
Fit for purpose validation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - validation of windwave dynamics against wave buoys - validation of primary producer density against remote sensing observations of chlorophyll-a
End Users/Stakeholders:	<p>Coastal managers, windfarm operators, aquaculture operators.</p> <p>Key Stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NLWKN; Lower Saxon State Department for Waterway, Coastal and Nature Conservation, Regional/local authority (data users and producers) - Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung (KDM) / German Marine Research Consortium; Non-profit Association of Research Institutes, Science Policy and Science Strategy (data users) - Gute Küste Niedersachsen (data users) - The Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH) (data users and providers)
Provider:	Hereon
Further Information:	None

2.2.1.3 Environmental impact assessment for multi-use operations in the Southern North Sea

<p>Application Objective:</p> <p>Developing an environmental impact assessment tool for large-scale multi-use operations to aid policy planning in the Southern North Sea.</p> <p>Within this application, an environmental assessment tool for large-scale multi-use operations (combination of wind farms and aquaculture) will be developed. By developing various wind farm and aquaculture management scenarios, their environmental impact will be assessed to support the Marine Spatial Planning Directive, EU Blue Deal and National policy planning (Dutch North-Sea policy, Dutch Marine Spatial Plan).</p>
<p>Application definition:</p>

The application focuses on the Southern North Sea, for multi-use wind-farm planning for a 2-year scenario study set in 2015 until 2017. The application will evaluate the interactive effect of wind farms and aquaculture on primary production and stratification near the wind farms.

Fig 2.2.1.3 Left: Difference in Total Inorganic Matter compared to base scenario without windfarms. Right: Difference in absolute salinity stratification compared to base scenario without windfarms.

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<p>The existing technology is an adapted 3D Dutch Continental Shelf Model (DCSM) with hydrodynamic and water quality modelling. This model uses the Delft3D FM suite , where D-Flow FM and D-Water quality are online coupled. D-Water quality will also be used to simulate sediment transport. This requires input from D-Waves, which will be used to model waves with offline coupling. Mussel and seaweed models developed in other EU projects, such as ULTFARMS and EDITO will be implemented for the Southern North Sea (Cornacchia et al., 2024).</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More stable temperature and salinity vertical profiles in deeper oceanic areas, resulting in higher accuracy compared to previous model versions.
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model validation with coastal data, when applicable (D2.1 Data Product 3.14)
<p>Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Update river inputs with the improved E-HYPE4 product (D4.2 Chapter 3) for the entire model domain
<p>Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving consistency in physics between CMEMS NEMO and 3D DCSM-FM on thermobaricity: taking pressure into account in the Equation of State. (D6.1 4.1.1)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Replace current Suspended Particulate Matter forcing with weekly CMEMS satellite data, gap-filled with the 4DVarNet deep learning algorithm. (D6.1 4.1.2)
Expected outputs/ target products- indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapped effect of multi-use on primary production: Difference in Primary Production compared to base scenario without multi-use wind farms - Mapped effect of multi-use on stratification (physics and water quality)
Fit for purpose validation:	Results from the reference simulation (without wind farms and aquaculture) will be compared with available monitoring data to assess the model's ability to capture temporal and spatial patterns in relevant hydrodynamics (temperature stratification, water levels) and biogeochemical variables (SPM, chlorophyll-a, nutrients, dissolved oxygen). This allows for identifying potential model drawbacks, which could induce uncertainties on scenario results.
End Users/ Stakeholders:	Dutch Ministry for Infrastructure and Water Management, Directorate-General for Water and Soil Affairs
Provider:	Deltares
Further information:	None

2.3 Applications related to natural and anthropogenic hazards and resilience to climate change (ESC 3)

2.3.1 Combating degradation of ecosystems through restoration and through support to strategic European coastal areas

In this section, the described coastal applications will support restoration actions through modelling and observing capabilities, and early warning systems

2.3.1.1 Supporting ecosystem restoration through modelling and observations in the Mediterranean Sea

Application Objective:

The objective of the application is to support ecosystem restoration by developing a science-based approach that combines modelling and observations in the Mediterranean Sea. It aims to enhance the understanding of the coastal protection ecosystem service provided by seagrass, and to support the definition of best practices for restoration.

Application definition:

The application focuses on the Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean, Italy), with reference to the LCFS (Lazio Coast Forecasting System) as the MSCS. It aims to develop an advanced vegetation module to be included in the coupled wave-circulation system based on SHYFEM-MPI and WAVEWATCH III.

The modelling approach is based on the downscaling of Copernicus Marine products released

at the regional scale of the Mediterranean Sea (MED-MFC).

The circulation core is three-dimensionally downscaled from MED_PHY, both for initialization and open boundary conditions, while the wave component is downscaled from MED_WAV at the open boundary. The parent model provides scalar wave fields to the child model, which are used to generate the spectral wave action using the Yamaguchi (1984) approach.

The following output variables are produced at hourly frequency:

- 3D: Temperature, current components, salinity
- 2D: Sea Surface Height, Significant Wave Height, mean wave direction, mean wave period, peak wave period, near-bottom orbital velocity.

The simulation will cover the period 2023–2024.

The application will improve the knowledge about the effect of vegetation on waves in terms of attenuation according to different phenotypes and seasons along the Lazio coast.

Figure 2.3.1.1: Maps of yearly averaged wave attenuation at the four Sites of Community Interest along the Lazio coast.

Existing Technology:

In Pillai et al. (2022), we implemented a seagrass parameterization in WW3 to modify the bottom friction equation by incorporating wave energy dissipation due to vegetation, based on the approaches by Dalrymple et al. (1984) and Méndez and Losada (2004). This formulation is the most commonly used for representing vegetation in phase-averaged wave models, where vegetation is approximated as rigid cylinders. Additionally, in this implementation, the phenotypic traits of the seagrass are fixed across the entire domain, not allowing to simulate different seagrass species within the same simulation.

Designed Improvements:

Advanced formulations for modelling vegetation now allow the inclusion of multiple morphological traits or plant species across the domain within the same simulation. The available observational data will support the development of a new parameterization for the seasonal variation of *Posidonia oceanica* leaf length, which shows strong seasonality in the region. Moreover, several studies have shown that the rigid cylinder approach tends to overestimate wave attenuation. Therefore, we propose an improved parameterization that incorporates plant flexibility to better mimic the dynamic behavior of seagrass stems. These enhancements will significantly improve the realism of vegetation representation in wave models for the Lazio coast.

Links with observations components (WP2/3)	For validation, data from D2.1 will be used, including sea surface height (SSH) from remote sensing (D2.1, product 2.1.1) Additionally, upcoming coastal data from D2.1 (product 2.3.2) will be used for validation with in situ observations.
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	Land-Ocean Continuum: Improved freshwater inputs for the Tyrrhenian Sea from D4.2 (product 4.1)
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	This application utilizes the MSCS “LCFS” system and inherits improvements from D6.1 and D6.2. The modelling framework will be enhanced with improved lateral boundary conditions, particularly through the implementation of methods for reconstructing multipartitioned spectra, and increasing the frequency of circulation inputs.
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	We will investigate the role of vegetation in wave attenuation through maps of wave energy reduction. The attenuation will be mapped and characterized across different Sites of Community Interest. Developing the yearly attenuation cycle will allow for a better understanding of how the seagrass effect on waves evolves throughout the year and across different substrates. The generation of bottom stress maps will provide crucial insights for designing well-planned restoration activities.
Fit for purpose validation:	The validation of the vegetation formulation unfortunately cannot be carried out using wave moorings, as no such observations are available. Therefore, we validate our results by comparison with studies found in the literature. The validation of the wave and circulation models itself will be performed using in-situ and remote observations available within the domain for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Temperature · Salinity · Sea level · Significant Wave height Key validation metrics include RMSE, bias, correlation, and scatter index.
End Users/Stakeholders:	Key stakeholders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Institute: Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) Thematic: coastal protection, nature based solutions · Institute: University of Tuscia Thematic: ecology, nature based solution, restoration · Institute: Consorzio LaMMA, Italy Thematic: modelling, coastal protection, extreme events
Provider:	CMCC
Further Information:	None

2.3.1.2 Tracking sub-regional MHWs in the Mediterranean Sea

Application Objective:

The objective of this application is to provide continuous monitoring of marine heatwaves (MHWs), which have strong impacts on marine ecosystems, from local to sub-regional scales in the Mediterranean Sea, through a user-friendly interface for its use by diverse stakeholders (e.g. scientific community, education, public, policy decision-makers and environmental agencies).

Application definition:

This web-based application is dedicated to the monitoring and visualisation of MHWs in the different sub-regions of the Mediterranean Sea (Figure 1). It provides continuous information about MHWs from event detection in real-time (using satellite observations) and prediction (using model forecasts) (illustration in Figure 1) to long-term changes in response to global warming (Juza et al., 2022). In the framework of the FOCCUS project, the application aims to improve the detection and prediction of MHWs integrating a new generation of high-resolution regional products (developed and assessed in WP2/3 and WP6/7).

Figure 2.3.1.2 Examples for the daily monitoring of SST on 2025-05-20. Map of marine heat spikes w.r.t. the period 1982-2015 in the Mediterranean Sea (left panel). Time series of daily SST averaged in the Balearic Sea in 2025 with detected MHWs as observed by satellites (orange) and predicted by model forecasts (yellow) (right panel).

This application currently uses daily sea surface temperature (SST) from reprocessed (REP) and near real-time (NRT) satellite products, as well as model analysis and 10-day forecast (MED-MFC), which are distributed in open access by the Copernicus Marine Service:

- REP SST from 1982 to 2023 (SST_MED_SST_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_010_021)
- NRT SST from 2024 to present (SST_MED_SST_L4_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_010_004)
- MED-MFC SST over the current year (MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013)

The portal is organized as follows:

- System description: definition and methodology applied, ocean datasets used, sub-regions of study, scientific references.
- Daily bulletin: daily monitoring of sea surface temperature providing MHW event detection in real-time and 10-day forecasts.
- MHW indices: annual MHW indices over the last four decades informing on long-term changes of MHW characteristics.

Existing Technology:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of daily SST products in the Mediterranean Sea from Copernicus Marine Service (REP-5km and NRT-6km satellite products, MED-MFC-4km). - Methodology from Hobday et al. (2016): MHWs are extreme warm ocean temperatures during prolonged periods, when SST are warmer than the 90th percentile of the climatological distribution for at least five consecutive days. - Reference period for climatology 1982-2015 (possible extension to 1982-2021)
Designed Improvements:	<p>The application will integrate the new generation of high-resolution regional products (observations and models) which are under development and assessment in WP2/3 and WP6/7.</p> <p>The extension of the reference period 1982-2021 is under consideration.</p>
Links with observations components (WP2/3)	<p><u>Regional satellite product</u> Merged sensors (L3S) SST : Spatial resolution of 1 km, from 2020-01-01 to 2020-12-31, Northern Adriatic Sea More details in D2.1: Data report (v1.0, december 2024).</p>
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	<p>N/A</p>
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	<p><u>Regional models</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WMOP: spatial resolution 2km, from 2024-01-01 to 2024-12-31, western Mediterranean Sea - AdriFS: horizontal unstructured-grid resolution ranging from 2.5 km in open sea to 300 m at overall coasts, Adric Sea <p>More details in D6.1: Model report</p>
Expected outputs/target products-indicators:	<p>Improved detection and prediction of MHW characteristics in the sub-regions of study.</p>
Fit for purpose validation:	<p>For satellite products, validation could be performed with the current REP satellite products and available in situ observation (e.g. mooring).</p> <p>For regional models, validation could be performed comparing them with satellite products and in situ observations.</p>
End Users/Stakeholders:	<p><u>Identified sectors</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Science and innovation 2. Coastal communities, beach and tourism 3. Coastal and marine management and governance 4. Marine conservation and sustainable ecosystem 5. Extreme hazards and safety 6. Climate and adaptation

	<p>7. Ocean health 8. Ocean weather and prediction</p> <p>Key Stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PortsIB or Port de les Illes Balears, public body responsible for managing the ports under the jurisdiction of the regional government in the Balearic Islands. - Conselleria d'Empresa, Ocupació i Energia. Direcció General d'Economia Circular, Transició Energètica i Canvi Climàtic. Servei de Canvi Climàtic i Atmosfera
Provider:	SOCIB
Further Information:	<p>Current application (before integration of new product)</p> <p>https://apps.socib.es/subregmed-marine-heatwaves</p>

2.3.2 Natural hazards and extreme events

In this section, the described coastal applications will address extreme events (coastal flooding, storm surges) and the improvement of forecasting systems to protect coastal communities from natural hazards.

2.3.2.1 Improve storm surge forecasts on the Atlantic French coast

Application Objective:

The aim of this application is to improve the storm surge forecasts of the national forecasting system for the French Atlantic coast.

The application will produce two types of independent indicators using two different methods to integrate processes not represented in the Tolosa-SW barotropic operational model:

- A two-dimensional map, derived from low-frequency filtering of the dynamics from larger scale models, will provide the water levels resulting from baroclinic processes at each point in the domain.
- A machine learning model will be used at several French tide gauge sites to produce a time series of corrections to be applied to the surge forecasts.

Application definition:

The application focuses on the French Atlantic coasts for a one-year period starting in autumn 2023. Although France is the Member State addressed by the application, the model on which the system is based represents a large part of Western Europe. The application is mainly a corrective method applied in a post-processing mode. The corrections will be applied to the outputs of storm surge forecast models, such as sea surface height and surge fields.

Fig 2.3.2.1 Left: Hourly average of the correction induced by baroclinicity to be integrated into the Tolosa-SW model outputs, for 01/11/2023 at 18:00 during the Ciaran storm. Right: Time series of surges observed (black), modelled by Tolosa-SW (orange) and corrected by Machine-Learning (green) at BREST during storm Kathleen.

Existing Technology:

The TOLOSA-SW model solves the non-linear shallow-water equations for variable bathymetry, including source terms for bottom dissipation, tidal forcing, atmospheric pressure, and surface wind. It allows for unstructured grids to achieve finer resolutions and employs low-dissipation numerical schemes effective for non-linear flows in the low Mach regime (Couderc et al., 2017).

The TOLOSA-SW mesh varies spatially from 100 meters on the English Channel-Atlantic coast to 10-20 kilometers in the northern part near Norway, considering bathymetric gradients and CFL constraints (Roberts et al., 2019).

The open boundaries of the simulated domain are forced with water levels from the FES2014b tidal model, an improvement over FES2012 with better resolution and altimetry data assimilation (Lyard et al., 2021). Other boundaries are treated as vertical walls, except for rivers with imposed flow rates. Wind stress is represented by a Charnock formulation with a constant drag coefficient, and atmospheric pressure effects on water levels are modelled by the inverse barometer.

Designed Improvements:

The first approach involves filtering the dynamics of IBI-ANFC (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00027>) and GLO-ANFC (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00016>) to extract baroclinic processes, such as dynamic variations in sea level or steric variations in sea level, excluding tides and atmospheric forcings. This method allows for 2D corrections but does not take account of errors resulting from lack of waves-induced effects on sea surface heights.

The second approach is based on the development of a machine learning-assisted calibration method. Several algorithms are

	<p>considered, such as Gradient Boosting or Long Short-Term Memory. These models use predictors associated with the 3D dynamics of CMEMS IBI-MFC outputs, along with meteorological and sea state data, and are applied on 1D time series.</p> <p>Assessing the impact of unrepresented physical processes on simulated water levels will improve the representation of physics within the system, thereby increasing the accuracy of the forecasting system. Estimating the impact of unrepresented physical processes on simulated water levels through Machine Learning will reduce the bias in the predicted storm surges and improve the accuracy of the forecasting system, both for deterministic and ensemble production.</p>
Links with observations components (WP2/3)	The satellite derived sea level heights (D2.1, product 2.1.1) will be used for validation tasks on 2D fields.
Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)	The rivers inputs from the E-HYPE product will be used as boundary conditions for the domain (D4.2)
Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)	The application will use the MSCS “Tolosa-SW” model system interfaced with the CMEMS GLO and IBI products (D.6.1)
Expected outputs/ target products- indicators:	<p>The application is expected to generate the following outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A two-dimensional map showing the ssh resulting from baroclinicity over the domain - Time series of corrected SSH forecasts for several French tide gauge sites.
Fit for purpose validation:	<p>The application will be validated using tide gauges and satellite data. The model's performance will be assessed during extreme storm events by comparing model forecasts with time-series of sea surface height obtained from observations.</p> <p>The statistics used for the validation part will include arithmetic bias (BIAS), mean absolute error (MAE), standard deviation (STD), root mean square error (RMSE) and the ECFAS indicators (Irazoqui Apecechea et al., 2023). The indicators will be calculated on time series, at the apex or over the entire storm events.</p>
End Users/ Stakeholders:	<p>Stakeholder : Météo-France (French weather service)</p> <p>End-users :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meteo-France Forecasters (operational production outputs) for authorities in charge of crisis management - French Ministry of Defense warning system

Provider:	SHOM-MO <i>i</i>
Further Information:	None

2.3.2.2 Improve storm surges and high sea forecasts in the Baltic-North Sea

Application Objective:

The objective of this application is to improve the forecast quality of sea level during storm surges and waves during high sea events. Storm surge forecasts in coastal areas with complex bathymetry like estuaries and fjords require models like HBMs that can resolve the estuary scales and can easily be adapted to the given conditions. The aggregation of wave forecasts on the other hand allows it to combine the best global and regional forecasts for a given area and time and to provide products with improved forecast quality for all European seas. The improvement will be demonstrated using established validation metrics for extreme events (peak errors) as well as general error statistics, e.g., BIAS and centered RMSE, in hindcast and/or forecast simulations. The goal is to improve the validation statistics of the coastal storm surge and wave forecasting systems with regards to short term predictions, a few days ahead.

Application definition: the area of interest of the application is Baltic-North Sea with focusing on Danish waters. Ocean model HBMs will be tested using two-way nested solutions in Randers Fjord (with resolution up to 50 m), together with CMEMS multi-year products; forecasts from DMI-WAM will be aggregated with CMEMS forecasts and observation data to produce better sea state forecasts. Expected results are shown in figures below:

Fig. 2.3.2.2 Left: Sea level in Randers fjord during North-Westerly storm in December 22, 2023, 06:00; Right: Aggregated modeled significant wave height during buildup of the October storm in 2023. Three satellite tracks with observed values at the same hour.

Existing Technology:

Storm surge prediction model:

DMI's operational storm surge forecasting system is HBM, a 6-domain two-way nested 3D coupled ocean-ice model covering Baltic-North Sea with North Sea open boundary conditions provided by climatological T/S, tides and surge sea level from a 2D shelf model. The resolution is between 0.2-5 km, with up to 56 vertical layers. HBMs is a relocatable ocean circulation model for on-demand coastal and shelf sea predictions, a further development

	<p>of DMI’s operational storm surge model. The model uses 2-way nesting capabilities to ensure adequate spatial resolution in highly dynamic regions and in areas with user defined applications (Berg and Poulsen 2012, Murawski et al, 2021, Frishfelds et al, 2025).</p> <p>Wave forecast model:</p> <p>DMI’s operational wave forecasts is produced by the 3rd generation spectral wave model WAM Cycle 4.5 (Hereon code repository). The model runs in a nested sequence of three computational grids: North Atlantic (25 km horizontal resolution), North Sea/Baltic Sea (5 km) and Denmark (1 km), to ensure that remote swell from the North Atlantic is entering the North Sea and the Skagerrak. The model runs 4 times per day at 00, 06, 12, 18 o’clock to provide a 5.5 days forecast.</p>
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<p>The improvements will include: i) improved bathymetry by using 50 m resolution bathymetry developed in Horizon Europe EDITO-Model Lab project and Danish bathymetry data; ii) improved lateral boundary surge sea level condition by using CMEMS NWS MFC products; iii) using the EDITO-Model Lab on-demand model builder HBMs to automatically configure FOCCUS applications; together with i), this allows a 2 way-nested 3D solution for river2sea continuum; iv) improving initial T/S conditions by nudging CMEMS T/S analysis in subsurface layers; v) investigate potential improvements by coupling WAM with HBM; vi) improving wave forecast, especially in situations of high seas, by aggregating CMEMS forecasts, national forecasts and satellite observations.</p>
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<p>Use of improved high-resolution Nadir satellite altimetry (Jason, Sentinel-3, Sentinel-6) 5Hz (1.4 km) (D2.1)</p>
<p>Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)</p>	<p>The configuration, river runoff and T/S observation data in Randers fjord in WP4 will be used</p>
<p>Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Improved lateral boundary surge sea level condition by using CMEMS NWS MFC products; Improving initial T/S conditions by nudging CMEMS T/S analysis in subsurface layers (D6.1) · Improving wave forecast, especially in situations of high seas, by aggregating CMEMS forecasts, national forecasts and satellite observations (D6.2)
<p>Expected outputs/target products-indicators:</p>	<p>Sea level, temperature, salinity and significant wave height The products will be available as 2D maps of surface parameters (sea level, SST, SSS, significant wave height) and time series at given</p>

	monitoring stations. Furthermore, model validation statistical parameters: bias, rmsd, correlation, etc. will be provided as well.
Fit for purpose validation:	Peak error, general error statistics
End Users/ Stakeholders:	Offshore operations, emergency preparedness Key Stakeholder: -Kystdirektoratet - KDI KDI is the Danish Coastal Protection Agency in the Ministry of Environment.
Provider:	DMI
Further Information:	None

2.3.2.3 Improve storm surge and extreme water levels forecasts in Portuguese estuaries

Application Objective:

This application aims to develop a short-term coastal forecasting service to predict and assess the impacts of extreme sea level events, including coastal overtopping.

This application adopts a two-tier approach to develop a short-term coastal forecasting service that predicts and assesses the impacts of extreme sea level events, such as coastal overtopping. Tier 1 focuses on the national scale, providing broad regional forecasts that capture large-scale hydrodynamic and wave conditions along the Portuguese coast. Tier 2 targets two high-risk coastal areas within the Tagus estuarine and coastal region, which are particularly vulnerable to overtopping. In these local demonstrators, high-resolution hydrodynamic and wave models are used to generate event-specific forecasts. By combining national and local scales, the application supports early warning systems, risk management, and the design of coastal resilience strategies tailored to both wide-area and site-specific needs.

Application definition:

The application focuses on two areas, an artificialized shore inside the estuary, in Cruz Quebrada coastal stretch, Oeiras, and in a low-lying sandy beach in Costa da Caparica, downdrift of the Tagus estuary. It aims to provide short-term service to predict sea level and wave conditions to support local coastal inundation models. These forecasts will support the prediction and assessment of extreme events such as coastal overtopping, addressing a critical need previously identified by local stakeholders.

The system uses existing hydrodynamic and wave models – MOHID and SWAN – at a resolution of 280 metres. These models provide boundary conditions for the high-resolution local model XBeach. The main variables considered in the forecasts include total water level, wave height and period, tide and surge levels, currents, and river discharge.

The results will support early warning systems and risk management strategies by providing maps and time series of predicted water levels and wave impacts at vulnerable locations.

Figure 2.3.2.3.1 Spatial domains of the MOHID and SWAN models, and the locations of the coastal stretches where the applications are being developed: Cruz Quebrada (Oeiras) and Costa da Caparica (Almada).

<p>Existing Technology:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3D operational circulation model (MOHID, 280 m) for the Tagus/Sado estuarine and coastal areas - Wave model (SWAN, 280 m) for the Tagus/Sado estuarine and coastal areas - Tier 1: National scale operational overtopping forecast using runup empirical formula forecast - Tier 2: Local overtopping forecast operational model 1D XBeach model applied to Costa da Caparica for overtopping analysis and morphology interactions (using SDB)
<p>Designed Improvements:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved accuracy in storm surge and extreme water level forecasts in estuarine areas - Fully coupled modelling chain (MOHID + SWAN + XBeach) for local-scale inundation forecasts - Dynamic use of satellite-derived bathymetry and river discharge inputs - Enhanced model resolution and nesting from CMEMS products to local scales
<p>Links with observations components (WP2/3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of updated bathymetry (e.g., Satellite Derived Bathymetry from WP2) as boundary input for local models (D2.1) - Use of total water level data to compare with numerical results (from WP2) (D2.1) - Use near real time data of river discharge in operational models (D2.3)

<p>Links with land ocean continuum components (WP4/5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporation of river discharge data into circulation (MOHID) and wave (SWAN) models(D4.4) - Enhanced representation of estuarine-coastal hydrodynamics and freshwater influence on wave propagation (D4.3)
<p>Links with integrated coastal model systems (WP6/7)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Downscaled/Nesting CMEMS products from national to local scale to better represent physical processes in the study domain (D6.1)
<p>Expected outputs/target products-indicators:</p>	<p>The application is expected to generate maps of flooding areas during predicted storm conditions and provide time series of total water level (TWL). These outputs will be integrated in the Atlantic SENSE platform.</p>
<p>Fit for purpose validation:</p>	<p>The application will be validated using reported event occurrences, and the TWL time series will be compared with TWL observations from WP2. Validation statistics will include arithmetic bias (BIAS), root mean square error (RMSE), skill score, and the Pearson correlation coefficient.</p>
<p>End Users/Stakeholders:</p>	<p>Civil Protection, Environmental Agency, Lisbon Port Authority, Municipalities (Almada, Oeiras).</p>
<p>Provider:</p>	<p>+ATLANTIC</p>
<p>Further Information:</p>	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Tier 1: Regional-scale, medium-resolution, first pass forecasting</p> <p>Tier 2: Localised, high-resolution, physics-based modelling</p> <p>TIER 1: National scale (first pass forecasting)</p> <p>TIER 2: Local scale (high-resolution forecasting)</p> <p>OPERATIONAL OCEAN MODELS: boundary conditions (waves, tides and storm surge)</p> <p>~25 km resolution</p> <p>~5 km resolution</p> </div> <p><i>Figure 2.3.2.3.2 Multi-tier forecasting architecture of the application. The system integrates operational ocean models (providing boundary conditions for waves, tides, and storm surge) with a two-tier forecasting framework. Tier 1 performs national-scale, medium-resolution forecasting as a first-pass screening of potential coastal hazards. Tier 2 is activated when Tier 1 thresholds are exceeded, running high-resolution, localized, physics-based models for detailed predictions in risk-prone areas.</i></p>

3. Navigating Forward: Next steps, Roadmap and Overcoming Common Challenges

Coastal applications designed through the FOCCUS project share several challenges towards success factors across data sharing (1), development procedures (2), and stakeholder engagement (3). These challenges have been discussed in round table sessions during the first FOCCUS General Assembly in Palma (March 2025). Addressing these effectively is key to enhancing the utility, and adoption of the coastal applications.

Among the common challenges, the first is **data sharing**, to ensure seamless access to data and tools across diverse user workflows. The numerical model outputs produced by the coastal applications are hosted at the producing institutes (WP8/9 partners). Currently, the commonly used storage solutions are internal project drives. The WP8/9 partners aim to find a common data storage and data sharing solution that is FAIR and can accommodate the large volumes of numerical model output data. The most sustainable solution is data sharing via the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean Infra (EDITO) [datalake service](https://pub.pages.mercator-ocean.fr/edito-infra/edito-tutorials-content/#/interactWithTheDataAPI) (<https://pub.pages.mercator-ocean.fr/edito-infra/edito-tutorials-content/#/interactWithTheDataAPI>).

The second challenge includes having **fit-for-purpose validation procedures**. Promoting a common validation procedure for primary variables (physics and biogeochemistry), could help ensure comparability across applications. We are currently working on such a common validation tool. Nevertheless, the validation of the downstream coastal application products, such as coastal erosion, harmful algal blooms, coastal inundation, shellfish aquaculture impacts, remain difficult to validate and must be evaluated on a case by case basis.

Thirdly and finally, FOCCUS coastal applications need to **meet local stakeholder needs**. Stakeholders have diverse and evolving needs, which require continuous engagement and adaptability. To overcome this challenge, it is emphasized to raise awareness about the availability and value of coastal applications through outreach and visibility, implementing strategies such as writing use cases for the Copernicus Marine website and communication via the [Copernicus Marine Forum](https://marine.copernicus.eu/about/national-marine-stakeholder-forum) (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/about/national-marine-stakeholder-forum>).

Local stakeholders should be actively engaged as the applications are being developed. Clearly defining the purpose and scope of each application (forecasting vs scenario simulations) will filter the interest of types of stakeholders, for which tailoring communication and functionalities could meet their specific needs. Finally, aligning applications with European Directives could ensure relevance for regional and national users bound by legal frameworks. These challenges are addressed together with WP10/11 on Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation planning; co-design and stakeholder engagement.

Annex

MS10.4 summary:

MS10.4: Co-Design Workshop was achieved by M6 of the project, led by MOI. This milestone was planned in two phases. The first phase encompassed a virtual technical co-design workshop on FOCCUS coastal applications with previously identified stakeholders which were contacted by various partners. In total, there were about 40 participants including ourselves as the project partners. This online workshop took place on May 13, 2024, and the agenda comprised of two sessions.

The first session focused on coastal applications and environmental/social challenges (ESCs) identified in the project, and included introductions to FOCCUS, overviews on the three ESCs identified (coastal protection/management, blue economy, and coastal hazards/building resilience to climate change), and a lengthy Q&A and discussion. The second session in the afternoon focused on technology discussions, and included deep dives into coastal observations, hydrology, and modeling systems.

The second phase was planned as one-on-one discussions between partners and the stakeholders identified, in order to facilitate more specific feedback and co-design. A questionnaire was created to help guide these discussions, which took place in the month of June between each respective partner and stakeholder. Summaries and details of these individual discussions were grouped in a joint presentation to enable further discussion and obtain overall themes of stakeholder feedback on the co-design process.

This event helped to advance the project activities and outputs by allowing the Consortium to build a clear picture of relevant stakeholders and start building relationships with them in order to find out how they could actually benefit from the project output, and what they would want/need in order to use the applications we plan to create as outlined in the DoA. This will help to ensure a strong uptake and awareness of the project output.

Milestone MS8.1 summary:

MS8.1 Applications Definition Workshop is a milestone led by partner CMCC which was delivered during M14 of the project. This milestone, originally due at the end of M13, was approved for an extension in order to align efforts with the planned all-Consortium meeting which took place on February 14, in order to maximize workshop participation among the Consortium members.

This milestone was achieved on Friday, February 14, 2025 as the culmination of a virtual all-Consortium meeting which took place from 9:30 to 13:30 CET on this day. There were around 50 participants online, including representatives from all WPs and all partners.

During this workshop, plans for the ongoing efforts of WP8 members in designing their applications, an outline for this deliverable, and future plans for the upcoming WP9 were discussed. This included outlining all of the proposed coastal applications to be developed in the project. Each category of coastal application was thoroughly discussed among the Consortium, broken down into the Environmental and Societal Challenges (ESAs) defined in the DoA:

- ESC 1 Management and protection of coastal area
- ESC 2 Enhance blue economy and multi-use operations
- ESC 3 Building coastal resilience to climate change

The full workshop agenda can be accessed here as the second half of the presentation:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jeczndHJz-Ys26rgpVQUXfohAK4FcDBODLtpb5XxuDQ/edit?usp=drive_link>.

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